

ORIGINAL RESEARCH**Autoregressive Distributed Lag Approach (ARDL) to Corruption and Economic Growth Nexus in Nigeria**Bassey Enya Ndem¹, James Tumba Henry², Friday Bassey Agala¹

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Abstract

The corruption in Nigeria is generating concern around the globe and among its citizens. This concern is because corruption has continued undermining the country's socio-economic development. Thus, this study empirically investigates the impact of corruption on economic growth in the Nigerian economy using annual data from 1980 to 2018. The study employed the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model as its estimation technique. In this study, economic growth was proxied by gross domestic product growth rate (GDPGR), while corruption was proxied by the corruption perception index. The result revealed that corruption has a negative and significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria in the long run. This finding implies that corruption has impeded the economic development process in Nigeria within the period of this study. Thus, it was recommended that anti-corruption agencies in Nigeria, such as the Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC) should be strengthened by enacting laws that will empower them to investigate, arrest and prosecute offenders.

Keywords: Corruption; Economic growth; Autoregressive distributed lag model; EFCC

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1. Introduction

Over the years, the Nigerian government has embarked on numerous reforms for economic growth, such as privatisation, banking sector reform, anti-corruption campaigns, and the establishment of organisations like the Independent Corrupt practices commission (ICPC), Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC), among others. These policies and agencies were adopted to ensure rapid economic growth and development and stem the country's rising tide of corrupt practices. Yet, the incidence of corrupt practices looms large in the country, from the military to the civilian administration.

Due to Nigeria's high level of corruption and how it affects economic growth, there is a continuing need to investigate corruption and economic growth in the nation. Nigeria's high poverty, inequality, unemployment, low standard of living, and general economic backwardness are believed to be traced to corruption. Corruption is a sickness that stunts any nation's cultural, political, and economic development and undermines the

efficiency of the government's many departments. In 2005, Transparency International stated that "corruption is one of the major issues of the contemporary world, undermining the good government, profoundly distorting public policy, leading to the misallocation of resources, harming the private sector development, and especially hurting the poor." Corruption in Nigeria is one of the numerous unaddressed issues that severely impede and limit development (Ayobolu, 2006; Ubi, Eko & Ndem, 2012). It continues to be a significant long-term challenge for Nigeria's political and economic growth (Sachs, 2007). According to the International Centre for Economic Growth (1999), corruption ranges from petty to political or systematic corruption and has eaten deeply into the country's fabric. According to World Bank studies, Abiodem (2007) estimated that corruption costs over \$1 trillion annually, or up to 15% of the GDP of a country like Nigeria. A cankerworm called corruption has slowed economic growth in all areas (EFCC, 2005). The difficulty in achieving rapid economic progress